

Unraveling the time evolution and *post mortem* changes of nanometric MnOOH during *in situ* chemical oxidation of
ciprofloxacin by activated PMS

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Abstract

Water contamination by synthetic organic compounds and effective methods to remove them are hot topics that deserve special attention due to their impact on human's life. In this work, nanometric MnOOH compound was synthesized (using a greener approach), characterized, and used to remove ciprofloxacin (CIP) antibiotic by *in situ* chemical oxidation using peroxymonosulfate (PMS) as oxidizer. The concentration of MnOOH (0.5, 1, and 2 g L⁻¹), PMS (1, 2, and 4 g L⁻¹), pH (3, 7, and 10), and morphological, structural, chemical, and electrochemical changes during/after use of MnOOH were investigated. The CIP molecule was completely oxidized and mineralized (> 60%) after 6 h under acidic conditions, without significant contributions of dissolved Mn(II) species. Low amount of intermediate compounds derived from CIP were detected by liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). CIP degradation was carried out by produced oxidants (such as HO[•] detected by electron spin resonance and LC-MS/MS) from PMS activation or, to a lesser extent, directly on the surface of MnOOH by direct electron transfer. The former was attested by high-resolution transmission electron micrographs due to formation of an amorphous shell structure (MnO₂) over MnOOH crystallites (using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements) with the consequent increase of the charge transfer resistance that hindered further electron transfer to the PMS oxidant.

Keywords: Catalytic advanced oxidation process; heterogeneous reactions; contaminants of emerging concern; hydroxyl radicals.

1. Introduction

The importance of water in our society is reinforced every day and mainly due to climate change that is leading to an unprecedented change in the hydrological cycle of water [1]. The consequences of climate change also reinforce forgotten problems such as water scarcity and quality for human consumption [2]. In turn, the quality of water for human consumption is directly associated to basic sanitation conditions, as well as to the type of treatment carried out for the supply and disposal of the water used [3].

Water contamination by organic pollutants of environmental concern, such as antibiotics, plasticizers, dyes, pesticides, and so on has been the subject of innumerable research papers [4–6] due to their persistence in the environment without being degraded and potential impact on human health [7]. Le Coadou *et al* [8] and Chow *et al.* [9] detected different amounts of synthetic organic compounds (hormones, pharmaceuticals, polyfluoroalkyl substances, and so on) at trace levels in bottled water in France and U.S. Other similar papers reported the presence of organic pollutants around the world [10–13]. As reported by Guo *et al.* [14], these compounds can lead to serious health problems to the human being as endocrine disruption, reproductive problems, cancer, cardiovascular disease, obesity, and diabetes. So, the development and use of technologies to treat different water matrices are urgent and deserve special attention.

Among the available methods to treat distinct water sources contaminated with organic pollutants, catalytic advanced oxidation processes [15] could be an option as it can produce highly oxidizing species, such as hydroxyl (HO^\bullet) and sulfate ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) radicals as well as non-radical species such as singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$). This latter oxidant is weaker than radical species, but highly selective and can react through electrophilic addition reactions and electron abstraction [16]. All these oxidant species can be produced through homogeneous catalysis using metal ions (Co, Cu, and Fe) [17], solid metal oxides (specially derived mainly from Fe and Mn) [18,19], and carbon-based compounds [20] starting from peroxydisulfate (PDS) or peroxymonosulfate (PMS) as main oxidizers. Once produced, HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals can react with organic compounds through [21] *i*) hydrogen abstraction, *ii*) electron transfer, and *iii*) addition-elimination.

Considering the *in situ* activation of oxidants by metallic oxides, Mn compounds stand out due to their abundant availability on Earth crust, low toxicity, and variable

oxidation states that enable electron transfer [22] Kamagate *et al.* [18] reported the importance of Mn(IV) in MnO₂ to oxidize norfloxacin antibiotic as well as the resultant Mn(II) to activate persulfate. The use of manganite (Mn^{III}OOH) showed similar performances towards organic oxidation and mineralization. The issue of Mn(II) leaching was investigated by Liu *et al.* [23] through the use of a carbon layer over Mn₃O₄. The carbon-coated particle exhibited low values of charge transfer resistance when using higher amounts of carbon, due to its role on the improvement of electrical conductivity and oxidant activation. Frequently, the time evolution of the Mn oxide catalyst during and after activation (*post mortem*) using distinct oxidants is not investigated and can be of great importance to design better compounds.

Thus, the aim of the present work is to synthesize, characterize and use nanometric MnOOH oxyhydroxide to activate PMS oxidant to degrade ciprofloxacin (CIP) antibiotic. Particularly, it is intended to investigate the influence of MnOOH and PMS concentration, solution pH, type of oxidant, and different water matrices on the PMS activation. Elucidation of the main working oxidants during CIP degradation by electron spin resonance (ESR) and identification of the main produced organic intermediates by liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry will be carried out. In addition, the time evolution of the MnOOH compound will be investigated by changes in its morphology, crystalline structure, superficial oxidation state, and electrochemical parameters to understand how MnOOH is deactivated. For such, high-resolution transmission electron micrograph coupled to *ex situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and electrochemical measurements will be also carried out. For the first time, the formation of an amorphous shell composed of MnO₂ over MnOOH crystallites was shown to be deleterious for further PMS activation due to an increase of the charge transfer resistance. The produced radical species resulting from PMS activation were also fully characterized by ESR and LC-MS/MS analyses using DMPO as spin probe.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Chemicals

All chemicals, including CIP (ciprofloxacin hydrochloride monohydrate, EMS), KMnO₄ (analytical reagent - a.r. Sigma Aldrich), C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁ (a.r. Synth), MnSO₄ (a.r. Sigma Aldrich), HNO₃ (a.r., Qhemis), NaOH (a.r. Impex), H₂SO₄ (a.r., JTBaker), PMS

(available as Oxone®, $\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot 0.5\text{KHSO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$, Sigma Aldrich), DMPO (5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrrolidine *N*-oxide, a.r. Sigma Aldrich), TEMP (2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-piperidine, a.r. Sigma Aldrich), $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (a.r. Synth), CH_3CN (ACN - HPLC grade, JTBaker), CH_3OH (HPLC grade, JTBaker), and HCOOH (a.r., JTBaker), and were used as received without prior treatment. All solutions were prepared using deionized water (Millipore Milli-Q system, $\rho \geq 18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$).

2.2 Synthesis of MnOOH

MnOOH was prepared according to the procedure reported in the work of Crisostomo *et al.* [24] with some modifications. Briefly, 50 mL of a 0.19 mol L^{-1} KMnO_4 solution was slowly added under constant stirring to a previously prepared solution containing 0.5 g of sucrose in 7.5 mL of water in the presence of 0.75 mL of concentrated HNO_3 . Then, 10 mL of a 0.65 mol L^{-1} MnSO_4 solution was slowly dripped to the mixture. The resultant solution was refluxed at $\sim 100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. After hot filtration, the brown solid product was washed with deionized water and vacuum dried in a desiccator.

2.3 MnOOH characterization and analyses

X-ray diffraction (XRD) were measured with Bruker D8 Advanced ECO instrument in the reflection mode with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation (1.54 \AA , 40 kV, and 25 mA) at a scanning rate of 1° min^{-1} from 10° to 80° (2θ). The surface morphology was observed by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) using a FEI TECNAI $\text{G}^2 \text{ F20}$ instrument.

The surface elemental analysis of MnOOH was carried out by XPS using a commercial spectrometer (UNI-SPECS UHV) with a base pressure lower than 10^{-7} Pa . The $\text{Mg K}\alpha$ line was used ($h\nu = 1254.6 \text{ eV}$) as the ionization source and the analyzer's pass energy was set to 10 eV. The inelastic background of the C 1s, O 1s, and Mn $2p_{3/2}$ high-resolution spectra was subtracted using the Shirley method. The composition was determined by the relative proportions of the peak areas corrected by Scofield's atomic sensitivity factors with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$. The deconvolution of the experimental spectra was done using a Voigtian type function, with Gaussian (70%) and Lorentzian (30%) combinations. The width at half height varied between 1.0 and 2.0 eV and the position of the peaks was determined with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ eV}$ with respect to the hydrocarbon peak located at 295.0 eV.

Electrochemical impedance (EI: ± 10 mV of perturbation from 5 kHz to 1 mHz) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements (20 mV s^{-1}) were performed in 0.1 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 (acidified with H_2SO_4 until pH 3) at ambient conditions and using a conventional three-electrode cell with a Pt foil and an Ag/AgCl (3 mol L^{-1} KCl) as a counter and reference electrode, respectively. The working electrode was composed of a carbon paper substrate as current collector, on which a slurry containing MnOOH (75% m/m at distinct treatment time – as prepared, 3 h, and 6 h) in the presence of XC-72 carbon (20% m/m from Cabot) and polyvinylidene fluoride (5% m/m from Sigma Aldrich) was deposited by drop coating. The slurry was previously mashed in an agate mortar and dispersed in 500 μL of N-methyl pyrrolidone. Before electrochemical assays, the as-prepared electrodes were dried at 60 $^{\circ}C$ for 12 h. All measurements were carried out in the dark.

To further confirm the oxidation state of manganese in MnOOH (before and during degradation experiments - see below), a potentiometric titration method originally described by Vetter and Jaeger [25] and adapted by Cheng et al. [26] was used. Briefly, 0.05 g of MnOOH was dissolved in 25 mL of a 0.25 mol L^{-1} $FeSO_4$ solution acidified with H_2SO_4 (eq. 1). Then, the solution was diluted to 100 mL with deionized water. The resulting mixture was titrated using a previously standardized 0.5 mol L^{-1} $KMnO_4$ solution (eq. 2) to obtain the first endpoint (V_1). Subsequently, $Na_4P_2O_7 \cdot 10H_2O$ (solid) was added to the previous solution until the pH value between 6 and 7 was reached. After that, titration was taken up (eq. 3) until reaching the second endpoint (V_2). The x value of the equations was calculated according to (eq. 4).

$$x = 1 + \left\{ \frac{5 \times (V_0 - V_1)}{2 \times [(4 \times V_2) - V_1]} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where V_0 is the endpoint volume of the same $KMnO_4$ solution in the blank titration, *i.e.* without MnOOH. The endpoint of each titration was determined using a potentiometer with a Pt electrode and an Ag/AgCl/KCl (3 mol L^{-1}) as reference electrode.

2.4 Oxidation and mineralization of CIP

The *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using MnOOH for the oxidation and mineralization of CIP (50 mg L^{-1} – see chemical structure in Fig. SM-1) was carried out in a glass vessel (1.5 L) equipped with a magnetic stirrer. The PMS solution was continuously added to the reaction vessel during experiments using a peristaltic pump at 0.12 mL min^{-1} . The effect of different parameters such as the solution pH (3.0, 7.0, and 10.0), MnOOH dosage (0.5 , 1.0 , and 2.0 g L^{-1}), and PMS concentration (1.0 , 2.0 , and 4.0 g L^{-1}) were evaluated. The solution pH was continuously monitored and adjusted by adding concentrated H_2SO_4 or NaOH solutions (5 mol L^{-1}). Other operational variables, such as the solution volume, treatment time, solution temperature, and stirring were kept constant at 1.0 L, 360 min, $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and 600 rpm, respectively. Samples were collected from the reaction mixture at predetermined time intervals, filtered through a $0.22 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ cellulose acetate cartridge, and quenched with excess $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (1.0 mol L^{-1}) unless residual oxidant were to be determined.

2.5 Analyses of degradation experiments

The concentration evolution of CIP was monitored by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC, Shimadzu 20A) at 270 nm and using a core-shell C-18 reversed-phase as the stationary phase ($150 \text{ mm} \times 4.6 \text{ mm}$, $5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle size, 100 \AA pore size, from Phenomenex®). A mixture of aqueous 0.1% (*V/V*) formic acid (eluent A) and methanol (eluent B) was used as the mobile phase in a gradient elution mode in the following sequence: from 10% to 90% of B in 10 min and then, back to 10% after 3 min. This last condition was kept for 2 min before subsequent analyses. The flow rate, injection volume, and temperature of the column were kept fixed at 1.0 mL min^{-1} , $25 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$, and $24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ respectively.

The intermediates formed during the CIP degradation process were determined by ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass analyzer (UHPLC-qTOF/MS), according to a methodology described in Text SM-1, in the supplementary material section.

The short-chain carboxylic acids were also determined by HPLC. For such, a Rezex™ ROA-H column ($300 \text{ mm} \times 7.8 \text{ mm}$, $8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle size, from Phenomenex®) as the stationary phase and a $2.5 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution as the mobile phase were used at 0.5 mL min^{-1} . The carboxylic acids were identified by comparison of their retention times with those of previously analyzed standards. The injection volume,

detection wavelength, and the temperature of the column were 25 μL , 210 nm, and 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

Inorganic ions were also analyzed by HPLC with a conductivity detector (Shimadzu CDD-10A SP). For anion determination, a Shodex SI-52 4E column at 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 3.6 mmol L^{-1} Na_2CO_3 solution at 0.8 mL min^{-1} was used as the stationary and mobile phases, respectively. For this analysis, a chemically suppressor system (Thermo ScientificTM ACRS 500) pumping a regenerating solution of 3.6 mmol L^{-1} H_2SO_4 at 0.8 mL min^{-1} was used. In the case of cation determination, a Shodex YS-50 column at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a mixture of 4.0 mmol L^{-1} oxalic acid and 6.0 mmol^{-1} tartaric acid solution at 1.0 mL min^{-1} were used without the suppressor system.

The amount of residual oxidant was determined using the spectrophotometric method adapted from the work of Liang et al. [27]. Briefly, 2.9 mL of a 0.6 mol L^{-1} KI solution and 0.06 mol L^{-1} NaHCO_3 solution were added to 1.0 mL of sample previously filtered. The resulting solutions were hand-shaken and allowed to equilibrate for 15 min before analysis in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800) at 352 nm.

Total organic carbon concentration ([TOC]) was measured with a GE Sievers Innovox analyzer. The [TOC] determination was performed after mixing a diluted volume of sample with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (30% *m/V*) and H_3PO_4 (6 mol L^{-1}) solutions. The TOC content was analyzed by subtraction of the measured values of inorganic and total carbon, in terms of produced CO_2 . More experimental details can be found in previous works of our group [28,29].

To identify the main working oxidant species, ESR tests were also carried out using DMPO and TEMP solutions as spin probes to confirm the presence of radicals (mainly HO^{\bullet}) and non-radicals ($^1\text{O}_2$) oxidant species, respectively. To elucidate the chemical structure of the main byproducts resulting from DMPO oxidation, LC-MS/MS analyses were carried out. All these experimental details can be seen in Text SM-2, in the supplementary material section.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of MnOOH

Figure 1a shows TEM images of the as-prepared MnOOH oxyhydroxide compound. As expected from the work of Crisostomo *et al.* [24], the catalyst's morphology exhibited a rod-like structure with a length and diameter ranging from 130

to 270 nm and 20 to 30 nm, respectively. To confirm the MnOOH nanoparticles' crystallinity HR-TEM micrography can be seen in Fig. 1b. The lattice fringe spacing was close to 3.4 Å, corresponding to the (11 $\bar{1}$) diffraction plane of MnOOH [24].

Figure SM-2 shows the XRD of the as-prepared catalyst whose diffraction pattern can be indexed to the JCPDS card number 41-1379. No impurities were observed in the XRD pattern, except for a peak close to 20°.

To further confirm the surface composition of the MnOOH, XPS analyses were performed. As showed in Fig SM-3, the high-resolution C 1s spectrum was deconvoluted into four peaks related to hydrocarbons (C-H) at 284.8 eV and to oxygenated groups of alcohol/ether (C-O type at 286.2 eV), carbonyl (C=O at 287.8 eV), and carboxyl (-O-C=O at 289.4 eV) [30]. The assigned carbon functional groups are typical and derive from surface contamination. The signals of O 1s were resolved into four peaks, as can be seen in Fig. 2a. The main components of all spectra are related to O-Mn (O²⁻) type bonds at 529.5 eV and hydroxyl groups (HO-Mn) on the oxide/hydroxyl near surface at 530.8 eV [30]. In addition, there are components of oxygenated groups resulting from contamination by hydrocarbons, such as O=C (530.8 eV), O-C (532.1 eV), and O-C=O (533.1 eV,) previously identified in the C 1s spectrum. Besides, the peaks of Mn 2p spectrum (Fig. 2b) were resolved into four peaks corresponding to MnO (640.7 eV), MnOOH/Mn₂O₃ (642.1 eV) MnO₂ (643.5 eV), and MnO₃ (645.0 eV) [30]. The above results confirm the successful synthesis of MnOOH.

3.2 Catalytic performance evaluation

3.2.1 Performance of MnOOH/PMS system on CIP decomposition

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the remaining fraction of CIP and TOC as a function of treatment time using 1.0 g L⁻¹ of MnOOH and PMS at pH 3.0. The catalytic and adsorption performance of MnOOH were first studied. As can be observed in Fig. 3a, ~25% CIP was adsorbed in MnOOH after 6 h, which is likely due to hydrogen bonding between pollutant and the oxygen-containing functional groups in the catalyst, such as hydroxyl [31,32]. The sole use of PMS led to 80% of CIP oxidation and only 10% of CO₂ conversion at the same treatment time. That behavior is probably due to the direct hydroxylation/dealkylation reaction on the piperazine ring of CIP by PMS [33,34]. When catalyst and PMS were combined, the CIP molecule was completely oxidized in 3 h, whereas 60% of mineralization was attained. To confirm whether the coupling was synergistic or not, CIP and TOC removal levels for the uncombined

experiments (control experiments) were summed, as represented by the dashed line (named as theoretical line) in Fig. 3. As the CIP and TOC removal levels using the MnOOH/PMS system were higher than the theoretical line (control experiments), a synergistic process was confirmed due to the *in situ* activation of PMS by MnOOH to produce powerful oxidizing species (see below).

3.2.2 Effects of solution pH

The solution pH is a significant factor affecting the catalytic performance of heterogeneous reaction. Thus, the effect of different pH conditions (3.0, 7.0, and 10.0) towards CIP oxidation and mineralization were investigated. Complete oxidation of CIP was attained in all studied pH conditions (~100% in 3 h), as seen in Fig.4; however, a slight increase in the pseudo-first order kinetic constant from acidic to alkaline solutions were observed, as can be seen in Table SM-1. That behavior can be explained considering the dependence of the CIP species (*i.e.*, cationic, zwitterion/neutral, or anionic) reactivity with solution pH as reported by Zhou et. al. [35]. In that work, the anionic and zwitterion/neutral species (pH > 7) were more susceptible to PMS oxidation due to the higher reactivity of the secondary amine in the piperazine ring. At alkaline solutions, $^1\text{O}_2$ oxidizing species can be also produced (eq. 5) [36], leading to a superior oxidation level.

An opposite effect was observed during TOC removal, *i.e.*, acidic solutions led to superior mineralization levels and rates. That behavior can be explained by *i)* the surface charge of MnOOH and *ii)* reactions mediated by singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), since metal oxides/hydroxides show a pH-dependent surface charging. As the pH for the point of zero charge (pH_{pzc}) was *ca.* 6.5 (see Fig. SM-4 - in agreement with literature [37]), it is expected that when the solution pH was over this value (7.0 and 10.0), the MnOOH surface charge was negative. So, PMS activation by MnOOH might be hindered due to electrostatic repulsion. In addition, the observed oxidation without significant CO_2 conversion is due to the produced low power $^1\text{O}_2$ species (eq. 5) specially at alkaline conditions [36].

To assess the possible effect of homogeneous reaction mediated by Mn(II) species leaching from the MnOOH compound at acidic conditions, IC experiments were

carried out. As seen in Fig. SM-5, high levels ($\sim 350 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) of Mn(II) were detected in the absence of PMS (only MnOOH and MnOOH+CIP). When using PMS, independently of the organic compound, low Mn(II) leaching values were measured ($\sim 25 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). In the solid surface, Mn(II) reduces PMS resulting in the formation of $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}/\text{HO}^{\bullet}$ and MnO_2 (*i.e.* Mn(IV) and catalyst deactivation) as already described elsewhere [37–39]. In solution, the possible formation of unstable Mn(III) from Mn(II) species (eq. 6 and 7) can lead to a disproportionation reaction resulting in the formation of low reactive MnO_2 (eq. 8). The Mn(III) species can also react with PMS (eq. 9) to produce $\text{SO}_5^{\bullet-}$ species and, possibly, $^1\text{O}_2$ (eq. 10) [40].

To investigate the possible effect of homogeneous reactions at acidic conditions, experiments were carried out in solutions intentionally contaminated with Mn(II) and without the solid MnOOH catalyst. As seen in Fig. SM-6, no significant oxidation or mineralization levels for CIP were observed in the presence of Mn(II) species, suggesting a negligible contribution of homogeneous reactions. A similar behavior was observed in the work of Anipsitakis and Dionysiou [38], in which distinct transition metallic ions (Co(II), Ce(III), Mn(II), Ni(II), Ru(III), and V(III)) were tested for the activation of H_2O_2 , PMS (HSO_5^-) and PDS ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$). In the case of Mn(II) ions, PMS can be activated leading to trapped sulfate radicals, as represented by eq. 11.

3.2.3 Effect of PMS and MnOOH concentration

The effects of PMS ($1.0 - 4.0 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) and MnOOH ($0.5 - 2.0 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) concentration on CIP oxidation and mineralization were investigated, as seen in Fig. 5. As expected, the oxidation levels and rates (Table SM-2) of CIP were enhanced at increasing concentrations of PMS. However, no significant differences for the CIP mineralization levels and rates were observed. A maximum of $\sim 60\%$ TOC removal was attained after 6

h. That behavior might be caused by the insufficient active sites on the MnOOH surface, which limits the PMS activation. The use of PMS concentrations higher than 1 g L⁻¹ can also result in an excess of unreacted oxidant (~30% and ~50% when using 2 and 4 g L⁻¹, respectively, of PMS), as can be seen in Fig. SM-7.

The investigation of MnOOH concentration led to no significant oxidation levels and rates of CIP from 0.5 to 2.0 g L⁻¹ (see Fig. 6), which confirms the hypothesis that the degradation of CIP is mainly influenced by oxidation with PMS. For TOC removal, a slight increase of 20% was noticed when the MnOOH concentration increased from 0.5 to 1.0 g L⁻¹ after 6 h, without further increments at 2.0 g L⁻¹. This result was not expected, since by increasing the amount of catalyst, a higher number of adsorption sites available for PMS activation would be expected. That behavior may be due to the observed agglomeration of MnOOH particles in solution, leading to no effective increment in the active area. Similar results were also reported for distinct heterogeneous system [41,42].

Thus, the optimized conditions considering TOC removal were acidic solutions (pH 3.0) using 1.0 g L⁻¹ of MnOOH and PMS at 25 °C. The remaining analyzes were carried out at this condition.

3.3 CIP degradation products and pathways: UHPLC-qTOF/MS and carboxylic acid determinations

For the optimized condition and considering the high levels of conversion to CO₂, only five intermediates were identified (see Table SM-3 and Fig. SM-8 for the total ion chromatographic profiles) using qTOF/MS analyzer (see Fig. SM-9 for the MS/MS spectra of intermediates). Fig. 7 shows the proposed degradation route, in which oxidation (probably mediated by HO[•], SO₄^{-•}, and ¹O₂) is initiated on the side chain of the piperazine group due its high electron density [43] resulting in products with *m/z* 348 and 362. After successive loss of two formaldehyde groups followed by an amine group, byproducts with *m/z* 334 and 306, and 263 were produced, respectively. In the final stages of CIP oxidation, the production of carboxylic acids clearly (mainly formic, acetic, propionic, and adipic acids – see Fig. SM-10) indicates the breakdown and oxidation of the aromatic ring, as well as the piperazine moiety before complete conversion to CO₂. The presence of F⁻ ion species was investigated, but led to no

reliable concentration values due to interferences in the baseline of the conductivity measurements promoted by the PMS salt precursor.

3.4 Time evolution of MnOOH: morphological, structural, and electrical analyses

To investigate and understand the morphological, structural, and electric changes taking place in the MnOOH catalyst during the CIP degradation, XPS, TEM, cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance, and Mn average oxidation state analyses were carried out before (as-prepared: MnOOH) and after (3 h: 3-MnOOH and 6 h: 6-MnOOH) treatment in the optimized conditions. For such, catalyst samples were collected at specific times (3 and 6 h), filtered, washed three times with deionized water, and dried under vacuum in a desiccator for 12 h.

The high-resolution C 1s spectra for the MnOOH at distinct conditions (as-prepared and after 3 and 6 h of treatment) can be seen in Fig. SM-11. As mentioned above, the assigned carbon functional groups are typical and due to surface contamination. For the 6 h sample condition, a $-\text{CO}_3/-\text{CO}_2$ termination group at 289.9 eV and a high binding energy component at 292.1 eV due to C-F_x termination were ascribed. This last finding is supported by the appearance of the F 1s signal ($\sim 0.3\%$ at.) at ~ 689 eV (data not showed). That behavior was interesting and may indicate a direct electron transfer from MnOOH to the CIP molecule (through the piperazine moiety). For O 1s, the main components of all spectra are related to bonds of the O-Mn (O^{-2} species) type at 529.5 eV and hydroxylic groups on the oxide/hydroxide surface at ~ 530.8 eV, as can be seen in Fig. 8a. In addition, there are components of oxygenated groups and those resulting from contamination by hydrocarbons (O-C at ~ 532.1 eV, and O-C=O at ~ 533.1 eV), previously identified in the C 1s spectra. For the 6-MnOOH sample, a CO_3 type termination at 531.8 eV and a component in the high binding energy region (534.6 eV) that could be attributed to molecular H_2O were also identified.

Some important features could be noticed from XPS measurements, such as *i*) an increase of the peak area related to the O-Mn binding (from 23.4% in the as-prepared sample to 37.3% and 39.1% after 3 h and 6 h of treatment, respectively) throughout the treatment process of the sample containing CIP and PMS, *ii*) a concomitant decrease of the HO-Mn components (from 45.0% in the as-prepared sample to 44.9% and 25.0% after 3 h and 6 h of treatment, respectively), and *iii*) appearance of foreign peaks after 6 h treatment, specially the C-F_x termination. These findings suggest that $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{OOH}$ is being oxidized to $\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}_2$, possibly supplying electrons to the oxidant (main process)

and activating it as well as to the CIP molecule. In addition, MnOOH may be undergoing an outside-in conversion reaction, that is, producing a core-shell compound (Mn(III) in the core and Mn(IV) in the shell) at the end of 6 h treatment and resulting in the material's inactivation. This last fact is supported by the observed decrease in the TOC removal rate and cessation of oxidant consumption after ~2 h (see Fig. 6b and SM-7), probably due to thickening of the MnO₂ layer that hinders electronic transfer to PMS (see discussion below). The C-Fx termination seems to confirm a direct electron transfer from MnOOH to CIP after a first step adsorption process (see Fig. 3a).

For the Mn 2p spectra, several components were used to adjust the experimental signal, as seen in Fig. 8b. For the as-prepared sample, the predominant signal was ascribed to MnOOH (or Mn₂O₃) at ~642.1 eV (44.6% of the experimental peak area), followed by MnO₂ (at ~643.5 eV - 23.4%) and MnO (at ~640.7 eV - 22.9%) components, as well as MnO₃ (at ~645.0 eV - 9.1%). In agreement with previous data, an increase of the oxidation state of Mn for the 3-MnOOH and 6-MnOOH samples were observed through decrease of the MnOOH signal and appearance of signals at higher binding energies. For the 3-MnOOH sample, a decrease of the peak intensity of MnOOH (from 44.6% to 32.5%) and an increase of MnO (from 22.9% to 41.5%) was noticed probably due to the initial leaching of Mn(II) ions (surface renewable). The intensities for the MnO₂ (19.5%) and MnO₃ (6.6%) peaks remained approximately constant. For the 6-MnOOH sample, an increase in surface oxygenation took place with the development of a peak ascribed to Mn₂O₇ at ~646.3 eV (6.7%). The peak intensity of MnOOH continued to decrease (23.4%) and that of MnO₂ (19.9%) remained at levels similar to the 3-MnOOH sample. The peak ascribed to MnO₃ increased considerably to 19.6%.

To further understand the evolution of Mn average oxidation state potentiometric titration experiments were carried out. As shown in Table SM-4, the average oxidation state of Mn in the as-prepared sample increased from 3.02 to 3.26 after 3 h and then to 3.356 after 6 h of treatment. This result confirms that Mn(II) in the MnOOH compound is being gradually oxidized to Mn(IV) and transferring electrons to CIP and mainly PMS. Such structural transformation was not confirmed by XRD whose diffraction pattern remained close to the as-prepared condition (Fig. SM-12); however, upon visual inspection of the assayed MnOOH compound, it can be readily attested a color change from brown to black (Fig. SM-13).

HR-TEM images of the as-prepared and 3-MnOOH confirm the appearance of an amorphous phase (shell) in the outer region of the MnOOH as seen in Fig. 9a, in contrast to a crystalline region in the inner part of the particle. Note that such structure, *i.e.* core-shell, was not observed in the as-prepared MnOOH (see the aligned fringes throughout the particle of Fig. 9b).

CV measurements (20 mV s⁻¹ and 2nd scan) for the 3-MnOOH, 6-MnOOH and as-prepared can be seen in Fig. SM-14. The electrochemical profile of the as-prepared sample is characterized by a capacitive behavior without clear oxidation and reduction peaks. That behavior is different from the one of 3-MnOOH and 6-MnOOH samples, in which an oxidation (0.98 V *vs.* Ag/AgCl (3 mol L⁻¹ KCl)) and reduction (0.81 V *vs.* Ag/AgCl (3 mol L⁻¹ KCl)) peaks (Mn(III) to Mn(IV) with Na⁺ ion intercalation) can be clearly seen due to the produced MnO₂ from reaction with PMS oxidant. The electrochemical impedance of those sample can be seen in Fig. SM-15. The equivalent circuit used to obtain best fits of the experimental data were composed of the solution resistance (R_{sol}), carbon material charge transfer resistance (R_C), and the oxide charge transfer resistance (R_{oxide}) at high and medium to low frequencies, respectively. The constant phase elements CPE_C are in parallel with the R_C element and CPE_{Oxide} with the double layer from the oxide material at medium to low frequencies, respectively. The time evolution of the R_{oxide} for the as-prepared, 3-MnOOH, and 6-MnOOH clearly shows how the resistance increase (from $2.9 \pm 1.0 \times 10^4 \Omega$ to $6.8 \pm 2.7 \times 10^4 \Omega$ before treatment and after 6 h, respectively) during PMS activation mediated by MnOOH, as seen in Fig. SM-16, hindering further oxidant activation. The increase of resistance can be also noticed when the total impedance (Z) of the 6-MnOOH sample is compared to the as-prepared sample in Fig. SM-15b.

3.5 Identification of the main working oxidants

The ESR spectrum resulting from reaction of MnOOH, PMS, and DMPO can be seen in Fig. SM-17. An intense resonance triplet line (1:1:1) was observed from N magnetic moment and resulting from two consecutive addition reactions in the adjacent alpha carbon atom. A less intense resonance line split into a 1:2:2:1 was also observed and attributed to the DMPO-OH (DMPO-SO₄ is unstable and easily hydrolyzed) compound (hyperfine constant $a^H = a^N = 16.1$ G – this value is slightly higher than the more common 14.9 G probably due to the presence of Mn(II) ions, variable ionic strength, and solution pH close to 7). To elucidate the main oxidation byproducts

resulting from DMPO oxidation, LC-MS/MS measurements were carried out as previously described. As can be seen in the extracted ion chromatogram of Fig. SM-18 and in the MS/MS spectra of Fig. SM-19, DMPO-OH (m/z 130.0860) and DMPO(OH)₂ (m/z 148.0966) compounds were detected. The proposed fragmentation route for each compound can be seen in Fig. SM-20 and agree with the works of Domingues et al. [44], Guo et al. [45], and Pavlovic & Hopke [46]. Thus, the triplet signal results from two consecutive addition reactions involving HO[•] radicals. For the experiments using TEMP, the obtained results were not conclusive as the characteristic triplet (1:1:1) were observed in the control experiment using PMS (1.0 g L⁻¹). So, only small modifications were observed when using MnOOH and PMS (see Fig. SM-21).

4. Conclusions

Nanometric MnOOH oxyhydroxide was successfully synthesized using a less harmful and greener reductor to activate peroxymonosulfate (PMS) oxidant under acidic conditions. In the optimized experimental condition, complete oxidation of CIP antibiotic (within 2 h) with more than 60% mineralization was attained after 6 h and without contributions from homogeneous reactions (*i.e.*, Mn(II) species). A low number and intensity of intermediate compounds were detected by LC-MS/MS due to the high oxidizing conditions leading to the production of carboxylic acid and inorganic ions. This latter was only detected on the surface of MnOOH after 6 h treatment by XPS measurements. Thus, CIP molecule might be oxidized through *i*) PMS activation promoted by MnOOH resulting in HO[•] radicals and, to a minor extent, *ii*) directly on the MnOOH surface through direct electron transfer. The former was attested by ESR measurements and to the structural changes taking place on the MnOOH surface, *i.e.*, increase of the oxidation state of Mn species by XPS measurements (rise of peaks at low binding energies and decrease of the MnOOH signal intensity) and potentiometric titration. The Mn oxidation state increase (MnOOH to MnO₂) led to the production of an amorphous shell structure (MnO₂) over MnOOH crystallites with the consequent increase of the charge transfer resistance that hindered further electron transfer to the PMS oxidant or CIP byproducts (no changes in the TOC values). That behavior may shed light on the synthesis of improved/engineered compounds to activate oxidants.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1 – **a)** Transmission electron microscope (TEM) image and **b)** high-resolution TEM (HR-TEM).

Fig. 2 – High-resolution XPS spectra of **a)** O 1s and **b)** Mn 2p for the as-prepared MnOOH compound.

Fig. 3 – Remaining fraction of CIP (CIP fraction) and TOC (TOC fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) for (●) adsorption performance of MnOOH, (▲) oxidation by PMS alone, and (■) oxidation by the MnOOH/PMS system. The theoretical line is based on the sum of uncombined experiments (- -). Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. 4 – Remaining fraction of CIP (CIP fraction) and TOC (TOC fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) at distinct pH values: (■) 3.0; (◇) 7.0; (☆) 10.0. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. 5 – Remaining fraction of CIP (CIP fraction) and TOC (TOC fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) at distinct PMS concentration values: (■) 1.0, (▶) 2.0, and (○) 4.0. g L⁻¹. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. 6 – Remaining fraction of CIP (CIP fraction) and TOC (TOC fraction) as a function of treatment time (t). Effect of MnOOH concentration: (♣) 0.5 g L⁻¹; (◇) 1.0 g L⁻¹; (⊙) 2.0. g L⁻¹. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 2.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. 7 Proposed degradation pathways of CIP in the MnOOH/PMS system. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. 8 – High-resolution XPS spectra of a) O 1s and b) Mn 2p for MnOOH at distinct conditions: as-prepared (MnOOH) and after 3 h (3-MnOOH) and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C).

Fig. 9 – High-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) for MnOOH at distinct conditions: **a)** after 3 h (3-MnOOH) of treatment and **b)** as-prepared (MnOOH). Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C.